

Film Kinetics of an Anionic Zn^{2+} Chloride Complex in Thin Layers of Strong-Base Anion Exchanger

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The kinetics of film diffusion of the ion-exchange system $ZnCl_3^-/Cl^-$ was studied dynamically at 20° in thin layers of strong-base anion exchanger (Wofatit SBW). The mass-transfer coefficient was found to be independent of the resin bed height; its value ranged between 0.44×10^{-3} and 0.83×10^{-3} cm/sec at Reynolds number ranged between 0.4 and 0.8. Interdiffusion coefficient was calculated and its value ranged between 1.41×10^{-5} and 2.19×10^{-5} cm²/sec. The time lag across the film (Nernst diffusion layer) was several orders of magnitude less than the half time of the film-diffusion controlled ion exchange. The value of Sherwood number was found to be in good agreement with that found in literature ($Sh=2$) for film-diffusion controlled ion exchange in the range of laminar flow under working conditions of forced convection.

Zn(II) forms two types of anionic complexes in hydrochloric acid solutions^{1,2}. In 0.1 M HCl exists the anionic complex $ZnCl_3^-$ while in 2 M HCl exists the complex ion $ZnCl_4^{2-}$ as the principal species in the aqueous phase¹. The former showed considerable adsorption in 0.1 M HCl on strong-base anion exchanger (Dowex-1) at room temperature in column technique¹.

The objective of the present work was to perform a thin layer ion-exchange filter for studying the kinetics of film-diffusion controlled ion exchange involving a complexing anion.

The liquid-film resistance can be characterised by a liquid-film mass-transfer coefficient whose value is a function of the physical properties of the system, characterised by the Schmidt number, Sc and the liquid flow characterised by the particle Reynolds number, $Re^{3,4}$. It is shown in the similitude theory^{3,4} that in processes of forced convection the Sherwood number, Sh is a function of Reynolds and Schmidt numbers. In case of film-diffusion controlled ion exchange in the range of laminar flow the value^{4,5} of Sherwood number is equal to 2.

It was recommended⁴ to start with a bed height not less than 4 mm of the concerned resin (Wofatit SBW) to ensure the establishment of a local exchange equilibrium in the column so that the ions moved in a sharp boundary through the exchanger bed. It was found⁴ that in case of pure film mechanism the mass-transfer coefficient was independent of resin crosslinkage as well as resin bed height.

Experimental

Anion exchanger

Wofatit SBW (8% DVB) resin in the chloride form was used as strong-base anion exchanger. The resin is

produced as aminomethylated spherical-shaped beads of styrene divinylbenzene copolymer in the chloride form by EKB Wolfen, in German Democratic Republic. The average particle diameter of the resin beads was 6×10^{-3} cm. The volume technical capacity of the resin was 1.39 meq/cm³ swollen exchanger. The density of the resin and its water content in weight per cent were 1.16 gm/cm³ and 43% respectively. The fractional void volume of a homogeneous packed column was equal to 0.4.

Zinc solution

The salt $ZnCl_2$ was used in A.R. grade for the preparation of the zinc solution in 0.1 M HCl. The concentration of the solution was restricted to the zinc ions only and it was 0.306 meq. Zn^{2+}/L , i.e., 10 ppm. The divalent zinc in the hydrochloric acid solution was easily determined fluorimetrically⁶. This method is based on the fact that the zinc complex of oxine fluoresces in ultra-violet light. A calibration curve was constructed by plotting the instrument (Corning-BEL 244 LTD-Halstead Essex England) readings against zinc content (mg/ml). This calibration curve was used for determining the zinc content of test solutions in the order of ppm.

Ion-exchange technique

The fixed-bed technique was used. In order to restrict the anions present in the whole ion-exchange experiments to $ZnCl_3^-$ and Cl^- , the zinc solution and the exchanger were taken in the chloride form. The apparatus used consisted of a glass-filter column with a G2 sintered glass as a base for the exchanger. The column had an internal diameter of 2 cm and a length of 30 cm above the sintered glass. The column was surrounded with a thermostated jacket to maintain the temperature constant at 20° with an accuracy of $\pm 0.1^\circ$. The ion exchange was carried out at a bed height, H of 4, 5 and 6 mm. The influent flow rate, W ranged

between 0.28 and 0.56 cm/sec and was controlled by the dosing pump $\frac{1}{2}$ DOB-PAE 32 which is produced by EKB Salzwedel in German Democratic Republic. The variation of ionic concentration with time was measured by collecting the effluent volume in portions of 200 ml; the amount of zinc in each portion was measured fluorimetrically with aid of the calibration curve.

Results and Discussion

The ratio of the metal ion concentration in the effluent to that in the influent, C/C_0 was plotted against the effluent volume in order to obtain the breakthrough curves (fig. 1). The breakthrough and the exhaustion points were chosen to be at 5% and 95% of the C_0 -value respectively⁷. The amount of $ZnCl_2$ exchanged

the degree 'of exchange, $\log(1-U)$ against the time of exchange, t (fig. 2). It is clear from equation (1) that the fractional attainment of equilibrium, U depends only on the magnitude of the dimensionless time parameter $DC_0 t/\delta r\bar{C}$ where D is the interdiffusion coefficient, δ thickness of the laminar interfacial film, r radius of the resin particle and $\bar{C}$ is the volume technical capacity of the exchanger. The quotient D/δ is the only unknown in equation (1) and can be easily determined from the slope of the linear functional relationship. This quotient is the mass-transfer coefficient⁹, β . From Table 1 it is clear that β increased with increasing

Fig. 1. Representation for breakthrough curves of the ion-exchange system $ZnCl_2/Cl^-$ in thin layers of Wofatit SBW resin in Cl^- -form at 20°C and various influent flow rates.

- a : H=0.4 cm ; W=0.28 cm/sec.
- b : H=0.4 cm ; W=0.39 cm/sec.
- c : H=0.4 cm ; W=0.47 cm/sec.
- d : H=0.4 cm ; W=0.56 cm/sec.
- e : H=0.5 cm ; W=0.28 cm/sec.
- f : H=0.6 cm ; W=0.56 cm/sec.

at a time, Q_t and that exchanged at equilibrium, Q_∞ were calculated from the breakthrough curves which were analysed by the graphical integration method.

According to Boyd⁸ :

$$U = Q_t/Q_\infty = 1 - \text{Exp.} \left(\frac{-3DC_0 t}{r\delta\bar{C}} \right) \quad (1)$$

a linear relationship which is a criterion for film mechanism was obtained by plotting the logarithms of

Fig. 2. A typical test of film mechanism for the ion-exchange system $ZnCl_2/Cl^-$ in thin layer (0.4 cm) of Wofatit SBW in Cl^- -form at 20°C and various influent flow rates,

- : W=0.28 cm/sec.
- : W=0.39 cm/sec.
- × : W=0.47 cm/sec.
- △ : W=0.56 cm/sec.

Re (referred to as homogeneous packed column of fractional void volume equal to 0.4) but it was independent of resin bed height, H. This result is an indication for the film-diffusion controlled ion exchange⁴. From equation (1), $t_{\frac{1}{2}}$, the time when the exchange reaction proceeds to $U = 0.5$, is given by :

$$t_{\frac{1}{2}} = 0.23 \frac{r\delta\bar{C}}{DC_0} \quad (2)$$

When the inverse of β is introduced in equation (2), $t_{\frac{1}{2}}$ can be easily deduced (Table 1).

According to Vielstich¹⁰ the effective film thickness is given as follows :

$$\delta = D/B = 3 d \text{Re}^{-\frac{1}{2}} \text{Sc}^{-\frac{1}{3}} \quad (3)$$

where d is the diameter of the resin particle. This shows the mass-transfer coefficient to vary as $D^{\frac{2}{3}}$, which

TABLE-1. KINETIC PARAMETERS OF THE ION-EXCHANGE SYSTEM $ZnCl_3^-/Cl^-$ AT 20°C IN THIN LAYERS OF ANION EXCHANGER (SBW) IN Cl^- -FORM.

W (cm/sec)	Re (-)	H (cm)	$\beta \times 10^3$ (cm/sec)	$t_{\frac{1}{2}}$ (min)	$D \times 10^5$ (cm ² /sec)	$\delta \times 10^3$ (cm)	Sh (-)
0.28	0.4	0.4	0.44	11.9	1.41	3.20	1.9
0.39	0.6	0.4	0.61	8.6	1.70	2.79	2.2
0.47	0.7	0.4	0.73	7.2	1.95	2.67	2.3
0.56	0.8	0.4	0.83	6.3	2.19	2.64	2.3
0.28	0.4	0.5	0.44	11.9	1.41	3.20	1.9
0.56	0.8	0.6	0.83	6.3	2.19	2.64	2.3

is typical of the results of boundary-layer calculation¹¹. Thus the last equation may be written as :

$$D^{\frac{2}{3}}/B = 3 d Re^{-\frac{1}{2}} \nu^{-\frac{1}{3}} \quad (4)$$

where ν is the kinematic viscosity. From equation (4) the only unknown, $D^{\frac{2}{3}}$ was calculated from which the interdiffusion coefficient, D (Table 1) was easily determined. The value of D is the resultant of the diffusion of both $ZnCl_3^-$ and Cl^- ions across the Nernst diffusion layer. The interdiffusion coefficient increased with Re, i.e., it is not constant. That means the exchangeable counter ions must have different mobilities¹². In view of the diffusion coefficient of chloride ions in HCl solution at 20° (2.73×10^{-5} cm²/sec)¹³ and according to the general rule which states that in an ion-exchange process the ion present in smaller concentration (hereby $ZnCl_3^-$ species) has the stronger effect on the rate of interdiffusion¹⁴, we can reach the conclusion that the values of D in Table 1 are expected to be more closely related to the diffusion coefficients of the complexing anion $ZnCl_3^-$.

From the values of D and β the thickness of Nernst diffusion layer was calculated ($\delta = D/\beta$)⁹ (Table 1). Its value decreased with increasing $Re^{\frac{1}{2}}$.

The time lag (equal to $0.42 \delta^2/D$)—i.e., the time which elapses until the diffusion of a species across a layer has attained the steady (or quasi-stationary) state¹⁵—was of the order of 0.13-0.30 sec. This was several orders of magnitude less than the half time of the film-diffusion controlled ion exchange between $ZnCl_3^-$ and Cl^- ions. Hence the first assumption¹⁶ on which the film mechanism is based, was quite justified, i.e., the diffusion across the film is fast as compared with the concentration changes at the film boundaries. The second assumption¹⁶ for film mechanism held in the present investigation less well as it is often¹⁶ the

case because it is assumed that the film thickness has to be much smaller than the radius of the resin particle.

According to the similitude theory Sherwood number is equal to^{3,9} :

$$Sh = \frac{\beta \cdot d}{D} = d/\delta \quad (5)$$

It was almost constant and had an average value equal to 2.15 (Table 1) which is in good agreement with that found in literature⁸ ($Sh=2.0$) at small Re. This is characteristic for film-diffusion controlled ion exchange in the range of laminar flow.

From the above discussion it was found that the kinetics of ion exchange involving a complexing ionic species is treated exactly as that involving simple counter ions⁴. The model under investigation can be considered as a systematic analysis of the performance of thin layer ion-exchange element to provide a useful procedure for studying the film kinetics under working conditions of Powdex-process¹⁷.

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